

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) ms_iii_031_100_sq

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: ms_iii_031_100_sq

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0057 A	Wavelength=0.71073	
Cell:	a=26.4195 (8) alpha=90	b=26.4195 (8) beta=90	c=17.5811 (5) gamma=120
Temperature:	100 K		
	Calculated	Reported	
Volume	10627.4 (7)	10627.4 (7)	
Space group	R 3	R 3 :H	
Hall group	R 3	R 3	
Moiety formula	C43 H69 N2 Na O12, 0.5 (H2 O) [+ solvent]	C43 H69 N2 Na O12, 0.5 (H2 O)	
Sum formula	C43 H70 N2 Na O12.50 [+ solvent]	C43 H70 N2 Na O12.50	
Mr	838.00	838.00	
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.179	1.178	
Z	9	9	
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.093	0.093	
F000	4077.0	4077.0	
F000'	4079.33		
h, k, lmax	36, 36, 24	36, 36, 24	
Nref	12982 [6491]	10793	
Tmin, Tmax	0.972, 0.979	0.952, 1.000	
Tmin'	0.972		

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.952 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.66/0.83

Theta (max)= 29.303

R(reflections)= 0.0540(7764)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1145(10793)

S = 1.007

Npar= 544

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

PLAT340_ALERT_3_C Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds 0.00567 Ang.
PLAT915_ALERT_3_C No Flack x Check Done: Low Friedel Pair Coverage 75 %

Alert level G

PLAT002_ALERT_2_G Number of Distance or Angle Restraints on AtSite 2 Note
PLAT007_ALERT_5_G Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms 8 Report
H1 H1W1 H2N H2W1 H4O H100 H1W2 H2W2
PLAT169_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains AFIX 1 Recds 1 Report
PLAT172_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains DFIX Records 1 Report
PLAT299_ALERT_4_G Atom Site Occupancy Constrained at 0.5 Check
O2W H1W2 H2W2
PLAT302_ALERT_4_G Anion/Solvent/Minor-Residue Disorder (Resd 2) 100% Note
PLAT304_ALERT_4_G Non-Integer Number of Atoms in (Resd 2) 1.50 Check
PLAT605_ALERT_4_G Largest Solvent Accessible VOID in the Structure 222 A**3
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels 5 Note
H043 H1W1 H2W1 H1W2 H2W2
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C2 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C3 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C4 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C5 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C6 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C7 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C9 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C12 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C13 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C16 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C17 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C18 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C20 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C21 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C22 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C24 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C25 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT850_ALERT_4_G Check Flack Parameter Exact Value 0.00 with s.u. 0.20 Check
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G Number of Least-Squares Restraints 2 Note
PLAT869_ALERT_4_G ALERTS Related to the Use of SQUEEZE Suppressed ! Info
PLAT899_ALERT_4_G SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL 2019/3 Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min). 3 Note
-1 2 0, -1 1 1, 0 2 1,
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 575 Note
PLAT913_ALERT_3_G Missing # of Very Strong Reflections in FCF 1 Note
-1 2 0,
PLAT965_ALERT_2_G The SHELXL WEIGHT Optimisation has not Converged Please Check
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 2.301 Note

Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 4.98 or SHELX Weight 11.37
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 1 Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
2 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
36 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
3 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
5 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
28 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 22/08/2024; check.def file version of 21/08/2024

